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ISC 2025

XX INTERNATIONAL SILAGE CONFERENCE

JULY 21-24, 2025 | GAINESVILLE, FL USA

CONFERENCE PROGRAM BOOK

HOST ORGANIZATIONS

GLOBAL FOOD
SYSTEMS INSTITUTE

ANIMAL
SCIENCES

UF | IFAS
UNIVERSITY of FLORIDA

UF/IFAS AGRONOMY
DEPARTMENT

FORAGE TEAM

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Name Badge

Your name badge is your entry pass to all networking events at ISC 2025, so please wear it throughout the conference. As a reminder, due to spacing constraints, *guests are not permitted*.

AGENDA-AT-A-GLANCE

Sunday, July 20, 2025	
3:30pm–6:30pm	Registration Opens Exhibitor Move-In Poster Installation
4:30pm–5:30pm	Planning Committee Meeting
5:30pm–6:30pm	Welcome Social
Monday, July 21, 2025	
7:30am–5:00pm	Registration Opens
7:30am–8:30am	Morning Refreshments
7:30am–8:30am	Poster Installation
8:30am–11:30am	Plenary Session
11:30am–1:00pm	Group Lunch & Presentation
1:00pm–2:00pm	Formal Poster Viewing - Session 1
2:00pm–5:00pm	Plenary Session
5:00pm–6:00pm	Networking Social & Formal Poster Viewing - Session 1
6:00pm–7:30pm	Dinner Banquet
Tuesday, July 22, 2025	
7:30am–5:00pm	Registration Opens
7:30am–8:30am	Morning Refreshments
8:30am–11:30am	Concurrent Sessions
11:30am–1:00pm	Group Lunch
1:00pm–2:00pm	Formal Poster Viewing - Session 2
2:00pm–5:00pm	Concurrent Sessions
5:00pm–6:00pm	Networking Social & Formal Poster Viewing - Session 2
Wednesday, July 23, 2025	
7:30am–5:00pm	Registration Opens
7:30am–8:30am	Morning Refreshments
8:30am–11:30am	Concurrent Sessions
11:30am–12:30pm	Formal Poster Viewing - Session 3
12:30pm–2:00pm	Group Lunch, Presentation, & Awards
2:00pm–3:15pm	Plenary Session
3:15pm–4:15pm	Formal Poster Viewing - Session 3
4:15pm–5:00pm	Closing Plenary Session
5:00pm	Conference Concludes
Thursday, July 24, 2025	
7:30am–5:30pm	Optional Off-property Field Tour

POSTER DIRECTORY

(Posters are listed in order by topic, poster session, then by presenter last name.)

POSTER VIEWING 1

POSTER VIEWING 2

POSTER VIEWING 3

Advancing Silage Production for Small Holders						
#	First Name	Last Name	Organization	Country	Abstract Title	Poster Session
1	Muhammad	Shaheryar	Bahauddin Zakariya University	Pakistan	Ensuring Quality Feed Through Silage-Making for Smallholders	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
2	Olabode	Olanrewaju	Calvary Ministries CAPRO	Nigeria	Silage, A Potential Solution to the Farmer-Herder Conflicts that Have Killed Tens of Thousands in West Africa- A Missionary's Perspective	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
3	Nouhoun	Zampaligre	Centre National de Recherche Scientifique et Technologique (CNRST)	Burkina Faso	Small Scale Corn Silage for Quality Fodder Conservation in the Integrated Crop-Livestock Systems of the Sahel	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
Aerobic Stability						
#	First Name	Last Name	Organization	Country	Abstract Title	Poster Session
5	Angelika	Borkowska	Volac International Ltd	United Kingdom	Amino Acids in Lucerne Silage: 2. Effects of Inoculation	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
7	Kristin	Rang	University of Bonn	Germany	Impact of Ensiling and Storage Temperature on the Aerobic Stability of Maize Silage	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
10	Hana	Synkova	NutriVet s.r.o.	Czech Republic	Monitoring Changes in Temperature of Fermented Feeds and Their Aerobic Stability	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
4	Mukti	Bhandari	University of Delaware	United States	Effect of Inoculant on Alfalfa Silage Challenged with Air Stress and Loosely Packed Conditions	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
8	Thiago	da Silva	Universidade Federal Rural da Amazônia	Brazil	Aerobic Deterioration of Diets Containing Cassava Shoot and Root Silages	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
6	Shane	Cronin	IFF Nutrition and Biosciences	United States	Effect of Laboratory Bag Silo Plastic Type on Fermentation of Corn Silage	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
9	Joao	Daniel	State University of Maringa	Brazil	Obligate Heterofermentative Lactic Acid Bacteria Decrease Losses During Storage and Feedout in Corn Silage Fermented for Long Period	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
Baleage and Other Silages						
#	First Name	Last Name	Organization	Country	Abstract Title	Poster Session
16	Joos	Latré	University of Applied Sciences and Arts	Belgium	Ensiling Moist Cereal-Legume Intercrops: A Promising Conservation Technique, Reducing Anti-Nutritional Factors in Faba Beans	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
11	Daniel Jose	Cavalli Vieira	University of Wisconsin-Madison	United States	Survey of Fiber Quality of Cover Crops Used as Forage to Dairy Cattle in Wisconsin	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
14	Ivan	Eisner	Novonesis	Denmark	Improving the Quality of Haylage for Horses by Adding a Biological Silage Additive	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
17	Anibal Coutinho	Rego	Federal University of Ceara	Brazil	Dry Matter Concentration Affects the Relationships with Variables Linked to Cassava Haylage Characteristics	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22

Baleage and Other Silages (continued)						
#	First Name	Last Name	Organization	Country	Abstract Title	Poster Session
12	Eric	Chevaux	Lallemand	France	Effect of the Inoculant and Grass Baleage Dry Matter on Fermentative and Nutritional Proliles	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
15	Francesco	Ferrero	University of Turin	Italy	The Use of Bale Compactor to Produce High Density Wrapped Bales of Several Forages and Grains	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
18	Eva	Wambacq	University of Applied Sciences and Arts	Belgium	Are Whole-Crop Silages of Cereals and Cereal-Legume Intercrops a Good Alternative for Maize Silage?	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
Forage Preharvest Management						
#	First Name	Last Name	Organization	Country	Abstract Title	Poster Session
19	Felipe	Amaro	Passion Ag	United States	Effects of Oxygen Barriers On Losses, Fermentation and Microbial Counts of Sorghum Silage	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
22	Kun Jun	Han	Louisiana State University	United States	Nutritional Value and Ruminant Digestibility of Different Sorghum Forage Types at Two Growth Stages	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
25	Matheus	Reboucas Pupo	University of Wisconsin – Madison	United States	Effects of Whole-Plant Corn Yeast Population on the Nutrient Composition, Fermentation Profile and Aerobic Stability of Silage Through a Meta-Analysis	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
34	Klaus	Hünting	Chamber of Agriculture of Northrhine-Westfalia	Germany	Impact of Dry Matter Losses on the Harvest Related Carbon Dioxide Emissions of Maize Silage	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
21	Ashley	Barkley	Lallemand	United States	Effects of Environmental Conditions and Management Practices on Epiphytic Microorganisms of Mixed Grasses and Alfalfa	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
23	Mark	Leggett	Volac International Ltd	United Kingdom	Amino Acids in Lucerne Silage: 1. Effects of Chop Length	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
20	Horst	Auerbach	International Silage Consultancy	Germany	Fermentation Quality of Lucerne as Affected by Year, Variety, and Cut	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
24	Maria	Mailhos	University of Florida	United States	Seeding Rate Effects on Morphology and Biomass Production of Sorghum X Sudan in Different Planting Seasons	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
Novel Technologies for Silage						
#	First Name	Last Name	Organization	Country	Abstract Title	Poster Session
13	Ludmila	Monteiro	Kansas State University	United States	Fermentation Characteristics, Aerobic Stability, and In Vitro Fermentation of High-Moisture Corn Varying in Amylase Expression	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
28	Haechan Mark	Bong	Polytechnique Montréal	Canada	Integration of Foundational Models on Autonomous Drones for Silage Inventory and Storage Quality Assessment	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
29	Flora Adel	Hoffmann	Hungarian University of Agricultural and Life Sciences	Hungary	Can Giant-Reed Silage be an Alternative Forage Source for Heifers and Beef-Cattle in an Arid Area?	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
31	Luiz Gustavo	Nussio	University of São Paulo	Brazil	Essential Oil Compounds as Additives for Rehydrated Corn Grain Silage	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
36	Juan Leandro	Monge	Universidad Nacional de Villa Maria	Argentina	Relationship Between Nutritional Variables of Pre- and Post-Ensiled Corn Crops: A Meta-Analysis	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
38	Lazaniriana	Randantoarimbola	Université Laval	Canada	Effect of Reducing Wilting Time and Adding Corn Grains and/or Soybean Hulls on Silage Quality	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21